

Spring brings new possibilities, and this spring finds the DDI initiative poised to move into new territory as more projects adopt DDI 3 in innovative ways. It is also time to renew our Web site to provide more interaction with the community. This issue of *DDI Directions* offers information about these topics and more...

Mary Vardigan, Director, DDI Alliance

DDI 3 Training Offered in Nairobi

Twenty-seven participants from INDEPTH/DSS sites representing ten countries from sub-Saharan Africa and Asia, the [APHRC](#) (African Population and Health Research Center), and the [INDEPTH](#) secretariat (Accra/Ghana) took part in an April workshop in Nairobi designed to provide participants with information about using DDI 3 in documenting complex survey data generated by the Demographic Surveillance System. **Wendy Thomas**, Minnesota Population Center, and **Joachim Wackerow**, GESIS, provided the training, which was supported by the APHRC and the INDEPTH secretariat.

New DDI 3 Projects Under Way

Several exciting new DDI 3 projects are emerging, many of which will be presented at IASSIST 2009:

Participants in the workshop on DDI 3 and the Demographic Surveillance System data in Nairobi, Kenya, in April 2009.

- **Joachim Wackerow**, GESIS, is creating a new version of an online tabulation system called **Exanda**. The new version generates DDI 3 inline ncube documents on the fly as well as common Web output formats. The user interface is internationalized. The original DDI 2 version is available (in German) with the [German Welfare Study](#).
- **Jostein Ryssevik** and **Pascal Heus**, Open Data Foundation, are working on the [SurveyLang](#) survey instrument project. This is a project to survey individuals about their language competencies in the countries of Europe. Export to DDI 3 will be enabled.
- **Pascal Heus** is also working on a **Question Bank** for the [International Household](#)

[Survey Network \(IHSN\)](#) with export to DDI 2 or 3 possible.

- There is a new version of the metadata export tool for [CSPro](#) that produces DDI 2- compliant metadata from computer-assisted interviewing. Support for DDI 3 is planned for future integration into the CSPro package.
- **Oliver Hopt** and **Andias Wira-Alam** of GESIS are working on a custom DDI 3.0 editor and a custom Web visualization tool for the **German Microcensus** (the MISSY II project). The predecessor information system [MISSY I \(based on DDI 2.1\)](#) is available (in German).
- The [Canadian RDC Network](#) and the [Institute for the Employment Research](#) (IAB) in Germany are working on DDI 3- related **metadata tools for restricted-use data**.
- **Alerk Amin**, Tilburg University, has designed **Questasy, an online data documentation system**, based on DDI 3, with an interface that allows administrators to easily manage survey data and metadata using a Web browser. The Questasy application has been integrated into the [LISS Data Archive Web site](#).
- **ICPSR and Survey Research Operations** at the University of Michigan have collaborated on a relational database schema that is DDI 3-compliant. SRO is using the database to enhance their tool for documentation of survey instruments – the **Michigan Questionnaire Documentation System**. ICPSR is using the database to drive its

variable-level search, called the [Social Science Variables Database](#).

Paper on DDI Published

Arofan Gregory, **Pascal Heus**, and **Jostein Ryssevik** of the Open Data Foundation have published a paper on “Metadata” for the German Council for Social and Economic Data. It is available for [download](#) (Working Paper 57).

IASSIST Offers Several DDI Sessions

Those attending [IASSIST](#) in Tampere, Finland, May 26–29, will have several sessions to choose from related to DDI, including two workshops. In addition, the **DDI Expert Committee meets on Monday, May 25, and the Steering Committee on Tuesday, May 26**.

Usability Group Refreshes DDI Web Site

The Usability and Outreach Committee of the Alliance is creating a **new version of the DDI Web site using Drupal**, an open source content management system. The UOG hopes to go live with the new site by fall 2009.

Dagstuhl Training to Be Offered

Back by popular demand, training in DDI 3 will be offered again October 25–30, 2009, at [Schloss](#)

[Dagstuhl](#) in Wadern, Germany, with **Wendy Thomas**, **Arofan Gregory**, and **Joachim Wackerow** as instructors. The following week, November 1–6, a session on future plans/current usage of DDI 3.0 will be held, with the final outcome a set of papers. For more information see: <http://www.dagstuhl.de/09442> <http://www.dagstuhl.de/09452>

European DDI User Group to Meet in Bonn

The International Data Service Center (IDSC) of [IZA](#) and [GESIS](#) are joining forces to encourage DDI adoption and proliferation. To that end, in December 2009 the two organizations will launch the first annual **European DDI User Group Meeting, or EDDI**. This meeting is being arranged by **Nikos Askitas** (IZA) and **Joachim Wackerow** (GESIS).

EDDI 09 will take place December 4 at the IDSC of IZA in Bonn, Germany. The day before on December 3, the [DDI Alliance](#) will sponsor a half-day DDI 3 training on “Putting DDI to Work for You!,” led by **Wendy Thomas**. See the [EDDI flyer](#) for more information.

First Annual EDDI
European DDI User Group Meeting in Bonn, Germany

Calling All DDI Users in Europe!

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EDDI 09 will take place December 04 at the IDSC of IZA in Bonn, Germany. The day before on **December 03**, the DDI Alliance (<http://www.ddialliance.org>) will sponsor a **half-day DDI course, "Putting DDI to Work for You!"**

Why You Should Attend

EDDI is designed to provide an annual European forum where DDI users from Europe can gather to discuss their work and their progress towards DDI adoption, as well as discuss any questions or challenges they may have about the standards.

EDDI will include presentations, poster sessions, and discussion sessions. The meeting will also offer a "hands-on expert" session in which users will have a chance to bring their "pain" of data with representations from the Technical Implementation Committee of the DDI Alliance.

EDDI in the Future

The philosophy of EDDI is to be an open, inclusive DDI community building activity. In this spirit, while IZA and GESIS and the IDSC of IZA will be running EDDI, with the IDSC of IZA being the main host, we strongly hope to have EDDI on the road across Europe so that the community converges at a different location every year where DDI is being adopted or considered for adoption. The host institution will then get a chance to appeal the DDI to its organization for that year.

Call For Papers

A call for papers will be posted at <http://www.iza.org/09442>. If you would like to be notified, please email your contact data to info@ddi-alliance.org.

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